

Gaza's Dire Need for Humanitarian Aid and Medical Mission Volunteers

Ponn P Mahayosnand, MPH.

Research Scholar, National Coalition of Independent Scholars

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8979-2806>

Correspondence: ponn@ncis.org

Keywords: humanitarian aid, medical missions, war Gaza, Gaza health

Dear Editor,

I am writing in response to Akhter's recent letter, *The Special Role of Medics in the Gaza Crisis* (1). As a Gaza war evacuee, I am often left speechless by such supportive words. As a public health research scholar, it is a duty to historicise these events, especially from my unique perspective. I have been specialising in Gaza Public Health Reform since 2020 (2), when my youngest joined her siblings as a medical student at the Islamic University of Gaza (which no longer stands). The destruction of the healthcare and medical education systems and the deaths of classmates, professors and healthcare professionals (which include family) make this research topic deeply personal (3), thereby causing delays in my ability to document necessary scholarly works.

As a Muslim public health professional, resources like the *Journal of the British Islamic Medical Association (JBIMA)* has enabled me to articulate my loss for words. I applaud Akhter's current call for humanitarian aid organisations to coordinate services to best serve Gaza's dire needs(1). I also praise El-Banna's call for the Muslim medical community in the UK to consider joining medical missions, written in *JBIMA's* April 2019 debut issue (4).

El-Banna opened with an ayah in the Qur'an, justifying his call to action as an Islamic duty of sorts. I commend *JBIMA's* board, editorial staff, and authors for adhering to the scope of this journal since its inception (5). Most strikingly, I am beholden to *JBIMA's* continuous and collective efforts to create a publication platform for our

community's unique needs while attracting and maintaining our unique voice. I wholeheartedly agree with the call for more medical missions to help tell Gaza's story (6). Notable examples include:

- An Australian Muslim doctor shared how Gazans are "not normal" with their faith, resilience, and ability to smile despite the devastation (7).
- An American non-Muslim nurse saying she would go back "in a heartbeat" and that the Gazan medical professionals who chose to stay are "heroes" (8).

Based on a recent mission, a British non-Muslim GP (general practitioner), with a speciality in public health, said Gaza will need 2-3 decades, not years, of recovery work (9). Therefore, medical aid missions to Gaza are crucial right now and for the unforeseeable future. Hence, I earnestly implore you to volunteer today.

Acknowledgements:

The author would like to thank Hafsa Shah, Samiha Ahmed, WS Chan, and ZM Sabra for their reviews and assistance.

References

1. Akhter M. The Special Role of Medics in the Gaza Crisis. *JBIMA*. 2024 Apr 30;16(6). <https://www.jbima.com/article/the-special-role-of-medics-in-the-gaza-crisis/>

2. Mahayosnand PP, Sabra ZA, Sabra DM. COVID-19 and Gaza: The Ideal Time to Establish a Medical Reserve Corps of Public Health Preventive Medicine Specialists. *Health Security*. 2021 Apr 8;19(2):235–9. <https://doi.org/10.1089/hs.2020.0192>
3. Mahayosnand PP, Chan WS. 2024. Can Online Petitions (e-Petitions), Open Letters, and Calls from Medical Doctors and Health Academics Influence a Gaza 2023-24 War Ceasefire and End of the Occupation? *JBIMA*, forthcoming.
4. El-Banna H. Humanitarian Medical Projects – A Message to the Muslim Medical Community in the UK. *JBIMA*. 2019 Apr 29;1(1). <https://www.jbima.com/article/humanitarian-medical-projects/>
5. Scope of Journal | Journal of the British Islamic Medical Association [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2024 Jul 10]. Available from: <https://www.jbima.com/scope-of-journal/>
6. Refaat in Gaza @itranslate123 If I must die, let it be a tale. #FreePalestine #Gaza <https://x.com/itranslate123/status/1719701312990830934> 2023; Nov 1. [cited 2024 Jul 10] [Tweet]. Available from: <https://x.com/itranslate123>
7. Bhimani A. Australian Doctor REVEALS Experience INSIDE Gaza [Internet]. YouTube: OnePath Network; 2024 May 23 [cited 2024 Jul 10]. Video: 28:11. Available from: https://youtu.be/pynvwAli_yo?si=2HDqiyw-53XTmEiA
8. Callahan E. American nurse who got out of Gaza describes desperation she saw [Internet]. YouTube: CNN; 2023 Nov 6 [cited 2024 Jul 10]. Video: 8:54. Available from: https://youtu.be/gk7iWgCk14U?si=rMghPavmZhol_VQk
9. Ferguson A. Doctor in Gaza: “I’ve never experienced anything like it” [Internet]. YouTube: Channel 4 News; 2024 Feb 14 [cited 2024 Jul 10]. Video: 8:23. Available from: https://youtu.be/UUUXZ8qGMWw?si=f_zgey9xDInRaJzK